

INFLUENCE OF LEADERSHIP STYLE ON SERVICE DELIVERY IN EMBU COUNTY GOVERNMENT, KENYA

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Abstract:

The implementation of devolved government system in Kenya has enabled most citizens to receive efficient and better services. This is facilitated by supportive leadership style such as democratic styles which enables different actors to participate in decision making and implementation of service delivery. The study objective was to find out how leadership style influences implementation of service delivery in County government. The null hypothesis stated that there is no significant relationship between leadership Style and implementation of service delivery in County government. This study adopted descriptive study design. The study made use of stratified sampling. Stratified is where the researcher divides a study area in portion and then he/she picks few individuals for study. The sample size comprises of 110 respondents. The researcher used descriptive statistics including frequency distribution tables, percentages. In addition to this, inferential statistical techniques were considered such as Pearson correlations and multiple regression analysis. They were used to establish relationships among variables. A detailed description of the data and the findings were presented in tables. The study found that county government has a policy on leadership style. It was also found that workers were not free to make most decisions without consulting their seniors, meaning decisions are made by their seniors. The study recommended that the County government should embrace participative leadership which may encourage implementation of service delivery in County governments and that county government employees should be allowed to air their grievances to the top county managers, avoid authoritative leadership in County government.

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1. Introduction

Service delivery is an essential function in the relation to government bodies and citizens. Strengthening of service delivery systems is a top significance of many global and national governments programmes as a way to improve citizens' lives (Hout, 2009). With the global service delivery context becoming increasingly complex, national government's systems are moving away from a focus on common citizens responses to more comprehensive systems. The global community agrees that without a system approach, service delivery outcomes will not further improve and related development goals such as the United Nation (UN)'s Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs) for 2015 will not be met.

A variety of global trends has led to a heightened awareness of distributed of resources, land issues at the international level. Population growth is placing rising demands on arable land, water and other natural resources and environmental degradation, exacerbated by unequal distribution of resources allocation (Porac & Thomas, 2014). Some governments are using central system while others are using devolved system (Humphreys et al., 2012). In America, the government of the United States (US) uses devolved system where the federal government of the republic has fifty states that constitute the United States of America, as well as one capital district, and several other territories. Some of the major challenges faced by US are uneven distributed of resources, racism among others (Pinter et al., 2012).

2. Statement of the Problem

The implementation of devolved government system in Kenya has enabled most citizens to receive efficient and better services. This is facilitated by supportive leadership style such as democratic styles which enables different actors to participate in decision making and implementation of service delivery.

However, the devolution has been faced by various challenges which include poor leadership, utilization of available resources and lack of national government support (Khalid, 2010). Poor leadership has led to poor service delivery and this is characterized by unequal distribution of resources during the last five years. The staff is not able to air their grievances and make decisions without consulting the top

management. This has led to low morale among workers and low productivity. A lot of time is also taken in decision making which affects the performance in service delivery.

2.1 Objective of the study

To find out whether leadership Style influence implementation of service delivery in County government.

2.2 Research Hypothesis

H₁: There is no significant relationship between leadership Style and implementation of service delivery in County government.

2.3 Significance of the Study

The study would be important to the various stakeholders since it highlighted the factors influencing implementation of service delivery strategies in County governments. First, the County government would use the findings to improve on their service delivery to its citizens. This would enable the citizens to access the services faster and efficiently. Secondly, the national government would benefit from the finding of the study where they would use them in formulating future strategies for the Counties, thus improving service delivery country wide. Researchers and academicians would also have a backup in researching areas of strategy implementation where the researcher could add in the new information to the scientific knowledge.

2.4 Limitations and Delimitations

The respondents were not readily available to provide adequate information as a result of their busy schedule. However, the researcher booked direct appointments with the respondents in order to reach them at their convenient times. Some respondents were uncooperative to the researcher hence failed to give information. The researcher tried to enlighten them on the significance of the study to the larger society. The scope of the study was limited to County government departments in Embu County which was purposely selected due to poor performance that has been there in first five years of devolved government. The study covered top and middle level staff responsible in the implementation of service delivery.

3. Literature Review

3.1 Leader follower theory

Leader-follower is simply where *“at any one time, leaders assume followers’ roles and followers assume leadership roles.”* Pitron says that the leader-follower implies a system of *“two or more individuals working together.”* Gilbert and Matviuk (2008) argue that within a leader-follower relationship *“followership escapes the box of simple subordination and obedience of structural tasks and opens up opportunities for innovative followership that produces and boosts growth within their leader.”*

Leader-Follower Theory goes further to explain the heart of relationship building and effective communication connections that must exist among leaders-followers and followers-followers. As followers become integrated in groups, they form group identities, a sense of competitiveness towards other groups and the need to actively influence desired outcomes. The group gain influence and they establish agendas, achieve collective goals, and gain group power. Thus, the group establishes its own leadership prowess that can be used to challenge or support their respective leader. The dynamics of the group’s social identity when applied to the leader-follower relationship can help leader’s decision-making capabilities (Hogg, 2001).

This theory helped the researcher to address leadership Style as a variable. The beneficial of this theory to this study is that it showed how relationship is important not only to the leaders of County government but also to the Counties and the employees. There is also higher job satisfaction and greater efficiency.

3.2 Leadership Styles

A study done by Hout (2009) found that leadership involves delegating more to employees and helping them to make most decisions without consulting their seniors. There are various types of leadership styles but the style chosen depends on the strategy that is adopted. The role of appropriate leadership in strategy implementation is very important. Leaders must develop new qualities to perform effectively and operate under leadership policy which fosters leadership styles (Saleem, 2010). There is impartially little practical confirmation on management in developing nations, but well-informed opinion and donor comment propose that noble quality management is in short supply.

The main forms of leadership styles that affect service delivery include; Participative, authoritarian, transformational and free reign. Authoritarian is one of the leadership styles of government in which state authority is imposed onto many aspects of citizens' lives (Hout, 2009). This is also known as dictatorship. According to a study

by Heifetz et al., (2012), organizations need to allow employees to have freedom in airing their grievances to the top management. This form of leadership does not allow the opinion of other leaders but only from the chief source.

Porac & Thomas (2014) conducted a study and found that public organization practice authoritative leadership. This affects the performance of employees since this managerial style does not invite input from employees on all company decisions. The staff is given pertinent information regarding organizations or government's issues, and a majority vote determines the course of action the company will take (Porac & Thomas, 2014). The main challenge in this leadership style is that a lot of time is taken to implement the policies since they must pass through parliament, accented by the president and publication in the government gazette. (Heifetz, & Laurie, 2012). Transformational leadership is another style of leadership where a leader works with subordinates to identify needed change, creating a vision to guide the change through inspiration, and executing the change in tandem with committed members of a group (Hout, 2009). This form of leadership style is a good though the main challenge is conflict of interest.

3.3 Conceptual Framework

4. Research Methodology

This study adopted descriptive study design. Descriptive design according to Mugenda & Mugenda, (2003) is the process of collecting data in order to test hypothesis or to answer questions concerning the current status of the subject under study. The study population for the study comprised of respondents from four departments namely public health, Administration and Co-ordination of County Affairs, Trade, Industry, ICT and Cooperatives and Agriculture. This included middle level and top level staff in the mentioned departments.

Table 1: Study Population

Departments	Frequency	%
Public Health	65	29.5
Administration and Co-ordination of County Affairs	42	19.0
Trade, Industry, ICT and Cooperatives	54	24.5
Agriculture	59	27.0
Total	220	110

Source: Human Resource Department Embu County, 2017

The study made use of stratified sampling. Stratified is where the researcher divides a study area in portion and then he/she picks few individuals for study. The sample size comprises of 110 respondents. The target population was separated into strata and sample of 50% of each stratum was selected. This ensured that all the strata within the study area were included in the study. Primary data was derived using questionnaires that had both structured and unstructured questions. The researcher used descriptive statistics including frequency distribution tables, percentages. In addition to this, inferential statistical techniques were considered such as Pearson correlations and multiple regression analysis. They were used to establish relationships among variables. A detailed description of the data and the findings were presented in tables

5. Data Analysis, Presentation and Interpretation

How leadership Style influence implementation of service delivery in County government.

Table 2: The County government has a policy on leadership style

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
County government has a policy on leadership style	41.91	49.10	9	2
Workers are free to make most decisions without consulting their seniors	19	7	18	65
Workers are free to air their grievances to the top management	66	11	15	7
There is Authoritative leadership in County government	74	22	8	6
Participative leadership is more effective in enhancing service delivery in County Government	84	16	8	2

The study found that 90% agreed that the county government had a policy on leadership style while 10% indicated the county government didn't have. This showed that there was a leadership policy within the leadership structure of County government. These findings are in agreement with those of Saleem (2010) who found that leaders must develop new qualities to perform effectively and operate under leadership policy which fosters leadership styles.

It was also found that 76.36% disagreed that workers were free to make most decisions without consulting their seniors, meaning decisions were made by their seniors while 23.64% indicated workers were free to make most decisions without consulting their seniors. This showed that majority of decisions were made by seniors and there was less in delegation. The findings disagrees to those of Hout (2009) who found that leadership involves delegating more to employees and helping them to make most decisions without consulting their seniors.

The study wanted to find out whether workers were able to air their grievances or not. It was found that 70% of the workers were free to air their grievances to the top management but 30% of the respondents indicated they were not. The findings are in agreement with those of Heifetz et al., (2012), who found that organizations need to allow employees have freedom to air their grievances to the top management.

The study wanted to establish whether the leadership in the county government was authoritative or not. It was found that 87.27% of the respondents agreed that there was authoritative leadership in county government while 12.73% indicated it wasn't there. The findings are supported by those of Porac & Thomas (2014) who found that public organization practice authoritative leadership. This affects the service delivery of employees since it does not invite input from employees on all company decisions.

The study also wanted to find out whether the element of participative leadership found in public organizations was more effective in enhancing service delivery in County Government or not. The results of the study noted that 90.91% agreed that participative leadership was more effective in enhancing service delivery in county government as compared to 9.09% who disagreed. The findings are supported by a study done by Kelly (2011) on the influence of participatory leadership in the United States and found that participatory leadership had a big role in influencing service delivery of government.

6. Hypothesis Testing

The study also made use of Pearson correlation in this segment as a technique of establishing whether there was any association that exists between the leadership style

and service delivery. Pearson's correlation is often employed to determine the existence of a linear correlation between two variables and occurrences that exhibit the existence of significant effect between the variables. The results of this exercise in the current study are as demonstrated in Table 3.

Table 3: Correlations of the dependent and independent variables

Independent Variable	Leadership Style	
Service Delivery (Y)	Pearson Correlation(r)	.689*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.003

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)

6.1 Test of hypothesis for the Variable Leadership style

From this exercise, it was deduced that there existed a significant and strong positive correlation between leadership style and service delivery as demonstrated by the obtained correlation of 0. 689. Further, from the exercise, it was established that the p-Value of 0.003 is < (less than) the minimum significance level (α), accordingly the indicated null hypothesis in the study; that a relationship between leadership style and service delivery does not exist is hereby rejected. From this, it was observed that the sampled data can be employed to the total study's population at 95% confidence level. This is in agreement with the findings of Porac & Thomas (2014) who found that public organization practice authoritative leadership and this affects the service delivery of employees since this managerial style that invites input from employees on all company decisions.

6.2 Multiple Regression Coefficients

Table 4: Regression Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.193	0.159		7.486	0.00
	Leadership Style	0.284	0.039	0.272	3.762	0.00

a. Dependent Variable: Service delivery

The study hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between leadership style and service delivery. The study findings revealed that there is a positive significant relationship between leadership style and service delivery ($\beta=0.409$, $t=4.639$ p value <0.05). This implies that a unit change in leadership style is associated with 0.409 increases in service delivery.

6.3 Model Estimation

$$Y = 1.193 + 40.9 X_1$$

Multiple regression analysis depicted that there was a positive significant relationship between leadership style and service delivery.

7. Summary of Findings, Conclusions and Recommendations

The first objective of the study was to set to establish the influence of leadership style on service delivery in Embu County government. The findings revealed that leadership style have a positive influence on the implementation of service delivery in county governments a case of Embu County. Results of the inferential statistics such as Pearson correlation show that leadership style has a major positive significance contribution to the on service delivery in Embu County government.

8. Conclusions

The study concluded that leadership Style influence implementation of service delivery in County governments. First, the study noted that the County government was governed by a policy on leadership. The study also explained that county workers were not free to air their grievances to the top managers. The study also noted that there was authoritative leadership in County governments. The results of the study noted that participative leadership was more effective in enhancing service delivery in County Government.

8.1 Recommendations

1. It was recommended that the County government should embrace participative leadership which may encourage implementation of service delivery in County governments.
2. The county government employees should be allowed to air their grievances to the top county managers, avoid authoritative leadership in County government.

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THE EFFECT OF EXTERNAL FACTORS ON PROFITABILITY OF
ACCEPTED BANKS IN TEHRAN STOCK EXCHANGE

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